

Design of a Double Butterfly Antenna with 60° and 90° Angle Reflector Comparison

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Abstract – An antenna is a device used for transmitting and receiving electromagnetic waves. The beam can be strengthened in the opposite direction and the gain of an antenna increased by adding a corner reflector to the double butterfly antenna to prevent radiation from spreading backwards. The quality of an antenna can be impacted by antenna characteristics. The antenna characteristics that were measured in this investigation were VSWR, Return Loss, Polarradiation, and Gain. At an operating frequency of 1800 MHz, measurements of a double butterfly antenna with reflector angles of 60° and 90° have revealed a VSWR of 1.99 and a return loss of -9.62dB. 7550 is the antenna impedance. 20 MHz of bandwidth. Three antennas operating at the same frequency are utilized for the gain measurement as comparison antennas. In this gain measurement, the reflector's angle is changed between 60 and 90 degrees. Based on the findings of measurements performed on a double butterfly antenna with a 60:90 angle ratio, a 60 angle reflector was used to achieve a gain value of 3.945dB. A gain value of 3.795dB is obtained at a 90° angle. So it is preferable to use a 60 Gain angle reflector rather than a 90 angle reflector.

Keywords: Radiation, Antenna, Reflector, Electromagnetic

Introduction

An antenna is a transition point between transmission lines in free space that serves as both a transmitter and receiver of electromagnetic waves. Antenna is one component that has a very important role in the communication system. An antenna that is regarded to be good is one that has a high efficiency. High antenna efficiency can be achieved by increasing the power radiated at the antenna while decreasing the power that can be generated on the antenna. On the receiving side, the antenna will receive electromagnetic waves and convert them into signals that the radio receiver can create. Meanwhile, the antenna on the transmitting side turns radio frequency (RF) energy into an electromagnetic field that is emitted into the air. A device capable of transforming electromagnetic wave signals on the transmission line into electromagnetic wave signals in the air and vice versa is required in the process of sending and receiving information signals. Double butterflies with an angle ratio of 60° and 90° constructed of aluminum may have an effect on the signal quality of an antenna. The reflector material, which is utilized for the reflector, is another component that might affect the efficiency of the antenna. The reflector is the back of the antenna that serves as a signal reflector and is physically longer than the driving one. The primary goal of positioning the reflector is to confine the radiation so that it does not spread backwards, but to amplify the beam in the opposite direction[1]. The advantages of this Double butterfly antenna include a simple shape, wide band and easy to make. In previous studies using reflectors with angles of 60° and 90°, based on the results of measurements carried out on the V double dipole antenna with the addition of a reflector angle of 90°, a gain value of 9.8 dB was obtained. At an angle of 60°, a gain value of 15 dB is obtained. So adding a 60° angle reflector is better than using a 90° angle reflector. The 60° angle reflector can increase the gain more, and the smaller the reflector angle, the higher the gain. After previous research, seen from the use of reflector angles

of 60° and 90° , the gain is increased by using a reflector angle of 60° compared to using a reflector angle of 90° in the V double dipole antenna. As a result, the author is interested in designing and conducting additional research on the double butterfly antenna using reflectors at angles of 60 and 90 degrees, so the title of this project is "Design of a double butterfly antenna with a frequency of 1800 Mhz and a reflector ratio of 60° and 90° angles".

Materials and Methods

Butterfly antenna

A bowtie antenna or also called a butterfly antenna is an antenna designed for a wide frequency range. This shape is an approximation of a wire dipole antenna in two dimensions. The Bowtie antenna is a development of the biconical antenna. Biconical antennas have a unique radiation pattern but tend to be bulky and impractical. Therefore, the biconical antenna was developed into an antenna that has smaller dimensions and is more practical, which is called a Bowtie antenna. Figure 2. shows a Bowtie antenna.

Figure 1. Bowtie Antenna

The main advantages of the Bowtie antenna are its wide impedance and simple design. Bowtie antennas are made of two triangular plates made of metal which are fed at both corners. This antenna is affected by the size of the triangular angle. But in making this antenna, the distance between the two triangular plates and the length of the arms of the two triangles must be limited. The length of the bowtie antenna arm usually depends on the manufacturer [3].

Reflector Antenna

The reflector is an element placed behind the driven which functions as a signal reflector with a longer physical length than the driven. Reflector is a tool or media that can reflect light and electromagnetic waves. The use of a reflector on an antenna has a function to change the radiation pattern and beam width of the antenna so that it can increase the gain of the antenna. The magnitude of the change in gain resulting from the addition of a reflector can be influenced by several things, including by adjusting the angle of the reflector panel (α) [2].

In order to be well received by the receiving system, we need an antenna that has a reflector. Reflector is useful for changing the direction of the diagram, increasing the gain. Reflector antenna is an antenna that is often used as a complement to the main antenna. The characteristics of a reflector antenna can be used for the purpose of changing the direction of the diagram, and increasing the gain. The types of reflector antennas include plane, angular, and paraboloid reflectors [4].

Figure 2. Flat reflector

Corner reflector

To more collimate the energy in the forward direction, the shape of the reflector itself must be changed to prevent the radiation from spreading backwards and being directed more in the angular latitude plane. One of the finishing arrangements is to fold it in half so that it forms an angle, as shown in Figures 2 and 3. This is known as the reflector angle.

In this Final Project, a 90° and 60° angle type reflector made of aluminum will be used to increase the antenna gain. The magnitude of the change in gain resulting from the addition of the reflector can be influenced by several things, including by adjusting the angle of the reflector panel (α), adjusting the distance between the driven element and the reflector panel (space), and changing the long dimension of the reflector (H) for the reflector with infinite sides [5][7].

Figure 3. Corner reflector

To determine the distance between the antenna (radiating element) and the reflector angle denoted by S, reflector height (H) and reflector length (L) can use the equation (1), (2), (3).

$$S = 0.5 \lambda \tag{1}$$

$$H = 0.6 \lambda \tag{2}$$

$$L = 2S \tag{3}$$

In this Double Butterfly Antenna, reflector angles of 60° and 90° are added so that with the addition of reflector angles of 60° and 90° it is possible to affect the signal quality of an antenna. The main purpose of placing the reflector is to limit the radiation so that it does not spread backwards but the beam will be amplified in the opposite direction. Using a corner reflector will obtain a slightly sharper direction, but only in the plane that crosses the fold of the corner shape [6][8].

Data collection

After measuring the parameters of the Double butterfly antenna with a ratio of reflector angles of 60° and 90°, the results are obtained from Return Loss, VSWR, Bandwidth, Polaradiation and Antenna Gain. The measurement results can be seen as follows:

Table 1. VSWR and Return Loss Measurement Results

Frequency(GHz)	RL(dB)	VSWR
1.79	5.51	3.28
1.8	9.62	1.99
1.81	7.3	1.09
1.82	14.7	1.45
1.83	5.67	3.19

Table 1 above explains how a VSWR value of 1.99 is obtained at a frequency of 1.8. and this antenna is deemed to meet the preliminary requirements, namely VSWR 2. Outside of the frequency limit, the antenna does not satisfy the requirements for use since the VSWR value is of 2 as at frequencies 1.78 and 1.83, the VSWR value of 2 signifies that it does not meet conditions and is not suitable for use. For further information, read VSWR, where the antenna fits the requirements and is a good antenna based on the VSWR value.

Radiation pattern measurement (Plane E) Angle 60°

The measurement of the polarization of the double butterfly antenna using a 60 angle reflector in the E field and the H field in tables 2 seeks to determine the shape of the antenna polarization that has been designed at an angle of 60.

Table 2. Polaradiation Results in the E Field and the H Field

Angle	E field average	H field average	Normalize the H fiel	Normalize the E fiel
0°	-59.84	-60.22	-47.7	-48.08
10°	-59.8	-58.98	-47.66	-46.84
20°	-35.4	-60.54	-23.26	-48.4
30°	-60.98	-59.44	-48.84	-47.3
40°	-60.56	-60.22	-48.42	-48.08
50°	-63.14	-59.88	-51	-47.74
60°	-61.18	-59.96	-49.04	-47.82
70°	-58.12	-57.92	-45.98	-45.78
80°	-59.744	-33.36	-47.604	-21.22
90°	-59.86	-57.88	-47.72	-45.74
100°	-59.02	-60.08	-46.88	-47.94
110°	-12.14	-60.24	0	-48.1
120°	-60.44	-58.74	-48.3	-46.6
130°	-61.82	-35.54	-49.68	-23.4
140°	-61	-59.86	-48.86	-47.72
150°	-61.54	-59.52	-49.4	-47.38
160°	-59.54	-36.14	-47.4	-24
170°	-58.76	-59.28	-46.62	-47.14
180°	-58.5	-60.1	-46.36	-47.96

Angle	E field average	H field average	Normalize the H fiel	Normalize the E fiel
190°	-59.06	-59.14	-46.92	-47
200°	-59.16	-59.18	-47.02	-47.04
210°	-58.68	-59.08	-46.54	-46.94
220°	-60.3	-60.1	-48.16	-47.96
230°	-59.64			
240°	-61.7			

Results

Table 2 shows the results of measurements of the E field pattern radiation at an angle of 110, namely -12.14 dB. And after normalization, it is positive, namely 0 (zero). And, as shown in table 4.5, the signal level is obtained at an angle of 80, which is -33.36 dB, while measuring H plane polarization. And the result of normalization is positive, precisely 0 (zero).

Figure 1. Polaradiation results of the H and E fields.

Results of Polaradiation were shown in this table, the E field and H field include the average results of two fields, namely the E field and the H field. There are additionally two normalizations at an angle of 60 in the E and H fields. The greatest value from the two average results for the E field and the H field is -12.14 dB at an angle of 110.

Conclusion

The double butterfly antenna has a VSWR value of 2 at a frequency of 1.8 GHz, which is equal to 1.99 with a return loss value of 9.62 dB based on the results of VSWR measurements using reflectors with angles of 60 and 90. At a frequency of 1.8 GHz, the return loss value obtained during reduction is 9.62. A good return loss

value is less than 5.51 dB. When the measuring frequency is 1.81, the return loss value is 14.7 dB, which is a very good value.

The bandwidth of the double butterfly antenna with reflectors at angles of 60 and 90 calculated from measurements and calculations in equation (11) using the formula $BW=F2-F1$ is 20 MHz.

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